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PREGNANT WOMAN WITH DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITRE

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Annotation. *The influence of diffuse toxic goiter on the course and outcome of pregnancy was studied. 67 pregnant women with diffuse toxic goiter were examined. The comparison group consisted of 38 pregnant women without thyroid pathology. The examination included determination of free thyroxine, TSH, autoantibodies to the TSH receptor and thyroid peroxidase in the blood of pregnant women and umbilical cord blood, as well as ultrasound of the thyroid gland of newborns and the TSH/free ratio. T4. In women with unresolved thyrotoxicosis, pregnancy and childbirth were more often complicated by the threat of miscarriage, gestosis, chronic placental insufficiency, fetal malnutrition and hypoxia, and untimely rupture of amniotic fluid. The high frequency of subclinical hypothyroidism (more than 50%) in newborns is associated with the transplacental transfer of thyreostatic drugs. Subclinical hyperfunction of the thyroid gland in 17% of newborns should be associated with the transplacental transfer of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor from mother to fetus.*

Keywords: *pregnancy; diffuse toxic goiter; newborns; thyroid.*

БЕРЕМЕННАЯ ЖЕНЩИНА С ДИФFUЗНЫМ ТОКСИЧЕСКИМ ЗОБОМ

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Аннотация. Изучено влияние диффузного токсического зоба на течение и исход беременности. Обследовано 67 беременных с диффузным токсическим зобом. Группу сравнения составили 38 беременных без патологии щитовидной железы. Обследование включало определение свободного тироксина, ТТГ, аутоантител к рецептору ТТГ и тиреоидной пероксидазе в крови беременных и пуповинной крови, а также УЗИ щитовидной железы новорожденных и соотношения ТТГ/свободный. Т4. У женщин с неразрешенным тиреотоксикозом беременность и роды чаще осложнялись угрозой выкидыша, гестозами, хронической плацентарной недостаточностью, гипотрофией и гипоксией плода, преждевременным излитием околоплодных вод. Высокая частота субклинического гипотиреоза (более 50%) у новорожденных связана с трансплацентарным переносом тиреостатических препаратов. Субклиническая гиперфункция щитовидной железы у 17% новорожденных должна быть связана с трансплацентарной передачей аутоантител к рецептору ТТГ от матери к плоду.

Ключевые слова: беременность; диффузный токсический зоб; новорожденные; щитовидная железа.

Introduction. Diffuse toxic goiter (DTG) is an organ autoimmune disease, the pathogenesis of which is based on the production of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor, which do not block, but, on the contrary, stimulate the function of the thyroid gland. The frequency of detection of thyrotoxicosis during pregnancy varies widely - from 0.05 to 3% [1–5,7,9,10,14] and requires clarification, since the clinical picture of thyrotoxicosis can be caused by other pathological

conditions, for example, gestational thyrotoxicosis, destructive thyrotoxicosis in autoimmune thyroiditis, toxic nodular goiter, trophoblastic disease [1–5]. Untreated thyrotoxicosis has an adverse effect on the course of pregnancy (threat of miscarriage, gestosis), childbirth (premature rupture of amniotic fluid, rapid labor) [5–9], as well as on the condition of the fetus and newborn [6,7,9–11]: risk of congenital anomalies, intrauterine growth retardation, stillbirth, the formation of intrauterine and congenital thyrotoxicosis [3,5,8,9,11–13]. To eliminate thyrotoxicosis during pregnancy, thyreostatic drugs are used: derivatives of imidazole (merkazolyl - MKI) or thiouracil (propylthiouracil - PTU), however, these drugs carry the risk of hypothyroidism in the fetus and newborn. It is believed that PTU penetrates to a lesser extent through the placenta to the fetus and into the mammary epithelium due to greater binding to plasma proteins [5,9,10,11,14–21]. There are separate descriptions of fetal development disorders (scalp disorder, choanal atresia) while taking thyreostatic drugs [3,9,20], but no convincing data on the teratogenic effect of MKI and PTU have been obtained [11,20,21]. The influence of thyroid-stimulating autoantibodies to the TSH receptor, which also easily pass through the placenta from mother to fetus, can be the cause of intrauterine and congenital thyrotoxicosis in 2–3% of newborns from mothers with DTG [3,10]. Its actual frequency, including subclinical forms, is unknown, since most women with DTG during pregnancy receive thyreostatic drugs that penetrate the placental barrier. The purpose of the study was to study the effect of DTG on the course and outcome of pregnancy.

Materials and methods of research. 67 pregnant women with DTD were examined. The age of the patients ranged from 19 to 37 years and averaged 27.4 ± 0.5 years. The duration of the disease ranged from several weeks to 7 years. In 52 women, the diagnosis of thyrotoxicosis was established before pregnancy, in 36 women pregnancy occurred while taking thyrostatic drugs, in 25, in the period from the 6th to the 32nd week of pregnancy, there was a relapse of thyrotoxicosis after remission of thyrotoxicosis by the time of pregnancy after conservative therapy (from 1 year to 3 years). In 43 pregnant women, thyroid disease was combined with autoimmune thyroiditis. All women with DTG received thyreostatic drugs during pregnancy: 38 patients took MKI and 29 took PTU. The initial dose of MKI was 20 mg/day, the “maintenance” dose was 5–10 mg/day. The initial dose of PTU was 100–200 mg/day, the “maintenance” dose was 50 mg/day. The functional state of the thyroid gland of patients before and during the use of thyreostatic drugs was assessed by the content of free. T4, free T3 and TSH in the blood. The average delivery time was 38.9 ± 0.2 weeks. The comparison

group included 38 women without thyroid pathology. The age of the patients ranged from 18 to 34 years and averaged 27.2 ± 0.7 years. The average delivery time was 39.3 ± 0.1 weeks. 38 children were born from mothers in this group. The average body weight of newborns was 3431.8 ± 55.7 g, body length - 51.7 ± 0.2 cm. The content of free thyroxine (free T4), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) and autoantibodies to thyroid peroxidase in the blood of patients and umbilical cord blood (Abs to TPO) were determined by the enzyme immunoassay using standard kits; antibodies to the TSH receptor were determined by the enzyme immunoassay using kits from DRG Diagnostics (Germany). To assess the functional state of the newborn's thyroid gland, the free level was determined. T4 and TSH in umbilical cord blood and the TSH/free ratio was calculated. T4, which was developed for the purpose of differential diagnosis of congenital subclinical hypothyroidism and physiological hyperthyroidism of newborns [23]. In both cases, there is an increase in the level of TSH in the blood, while free. T4 in subclinical hypothyroidism tends to decrease, and in neonatal hyperthyroidism it tends to increase. In healthy newborns, the TSH/free ratio is T4 fluctuates at $p = 0.001$ from 0.27 to 0.72. Values outside the specified limits indicate the presence of hypothyroidism or hyperthyroidism in the newborn. In women without thyroid pathology, there was a significant decrease in free. T4 throughout pregnancy, which is associated with an increase in thyroxine-binding globulin in the blood. However, the TSH level did not change significantly during pregnancy. Ultrasonography of the newborn's thyroid gland was performed on days 4–7 of life using a multifrequency sensor (frequency 6.9 MHz) on a Voluson 730, Expert GE device. Measurement of the thyroid lobes was performed using longitudinal and transverse scanning. The volume of the thyroid gland was calculated using the formula J. Brunn [22]. The average size of the thyroid gland in newborns from mothers from the comparison group was 0.60 ± 0.01 cm³ ($p < 0.001$). The range of fluctuations of this indicator ($p = 0.001$) varied from 0.36 to 0.71 cm³. The results obtained were processed using the standard SPSS program (version 6.0) on a personal computer using the variation statistics method. The hypothesis of equality of two means was tested using Student's t-test. Differences between the compared values were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and its discussion. The frequency of complications of pregnancy and childbirth in the examined women is presented. In women with DTG and unresolved thyrotoxicosis, pregnancy was more often complicated by early toxicosis, threat of miscarriage, spontaneous miscarriages, chronic placental insufficiency, gestosis and fetal malnutrition. Against the background of

eliminated thyrotoxicosis, the frequency of these complications was significantly lower, but still exceeded these indicators in the comparison group. The most common complications of childbirth in women with DTG were premature birth, untimely rupture of amniotic fluid, and fetal hypoxia. The frequency of labor anomalies and operative delivery significantly exceeded these indicators in the comparison groups. The incidence of complications of pregnancy and childbirth was significantly lower in the group of pregnant women with DTG receiving thyrostatic therapy, compared with these indicators in pregnant women with DTG with unresolved thyrotoxicosis. The period of delivery in the group of women with DTG varied from 34 to 41 weeks and averaged 38.6 ± 0.2 weeks, which was noticeably different from the indicator (39.3 ± 0.2 weeks) ($p < 0.05$) in the group comparisons. All women with DTG showed a decrease in the level of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor at the time of delivery. 68 living children (one twin) were born to mothers with DTD. Height and weight indicators and Apgar scores of newborns from mothers with DTD are presented. The average body weight of full-term newborns from mothers with DTD (3279.2 ± 55.8 g) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than in the comparison group (3480 ± 74.9 g). Functional parameters of the thyroid gland in newborns varied widely. According to the TSH/free ratio. T4, 36 newborns from mothers with DTG were diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism, 11 with subclinical hyperthyroidism, and in 21 newborns, indicators of the functional state of the thyroid gland did not go beyond physiological values. Hyperthyroidism in newborns of mothers with DTG can be associated with the transplacental transfer of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor, which is confirmed by a higher level of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor in newborns with subclinical hyperthyroidism. Clinically significant congenital thyrotoxicosis was diagnosed in only one newborn (TSH/free T4 ratio was 0.002). The level of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor in the umbilical cord blood of this child was 36.9 IU/L. In 36 of 68 newborns from mothers with DTG, subclinical hypothyroidism was detected (TSH/free T4 coefficient more than 0.72, average value - 1.1 ± 0.1). The average TSH level in the blood of newborns with subclinical hypothyroidism was significantly higher than this indicator in the blood of newborns from mothers without thyroid pathology, while the content of free. T4 did not differ in the compared groups. Hypofunction of the thyroid gland was detected mainly in newborns from mothers who took thyreostatic drugs in the second and third trimesters of pregnancy. Subclinical hypothyroidism was diagnosed in 20 of 39 newborns ($51.3 \pm 8.0\%$) whose mothers received MCI and in 16 of 29 newborns ($55.2 \pm 9.2\%$) whose mothers received PTU during

pregnancy. The results obtained confirm the data on the possibility of transplacental transfer of PTU [24].

Conclusions

1. With diffuse toxic goiter, pregnancy is often complicated by gestosis, chronic placental insufficiency, fetal malnutrition, untimely rupture of amniotic fluid, and premature birth.

2. The volume of the thyroid gland in newborns from mothers with thyroid disease significantly exceeds the volume of the thyroid gland in newborns from mothers without thyroid pathology, which is likely due to the transplacental transfer of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor from mother to fetus.

3. In 17% of newborns from mothers with DTG, hyperfunction of the thyroid gland is detected, caused by the transplacental transfer from mother to fetus of autoantibodies to the TSH receptor. Explicit thyrotoxicosis is relatively rare among the total number of children from mothers with thyrotoxicosis (1.4%).

4. In 52% of newborns from mothers with DTG, subclinical hypothyroidism is detected (average TSH - 13.6 ± 0.9 mIU/l, average free T4 - 12.6 ± 0.4 pmol/l, average TSH/free coefficient T4 1.1 ± 0.1), probably due to the transplacental transfer of thyreostatic drugs, derivatives of both imidazole and thiouracil.

5. In newborns from mothers with DTG who received thyreostatic therapy throughout pregnancy, hypofunction of the thyroid gland (TSH/free T4 coefficient 1.34 ± 0.2) occurs significantly ($p < 0.05$) more often than among newborns mothers whose thyreostatic therapy was discontinued at an earlier stage (before the third trimester) (average TSH/free T4 ratio 0.82 ± 0.1).

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